

Development of Treatments for Psychological Patients from a Turkish Perspective

Sema ERDUGAN

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Express English Education,
ORCID ID: 0009-0007-4615-3466,
Email: sema@expressenglish.com.tr

ABSTRACT

The summary of the research focuses on the status of psychological illnesses in Turkey, the current treatment approaches to these illnesses, and the policies and regulations in this field. This comprehensive analysis examines the historical development of psychology in Turkey and its impact on modern treatment methods, while also evaluating how these treatment methods integrate with the societal and cultural structure.

The research investigates the role of psychology education and the training of professional practitioners in the evolution of treatment approaches, as well as the contributions of technological innovations to

psychological treatments. It reveals that the mental health policies and regulations in Turkey are focused on improving the quality of services, raising societal awareness, and reducing the stigmatization of psychological illnesses. Additionally, the research emphasizes that these policies prioritize the development of new treatment methods through research and innovation, early diagnosis and intervention, enhancing societal psychological well-being, and developing specialized programs for disadvantaged groups.

In conclusion, the research demonstrates that Turkey's mental health policies and practices are focused on improving mental health across the society within a continuously evolving and innovative strategic framework. This approach is aimed at providing effective and innovative solutions in the field of mental health, both at the national level and within the context of international collaborations.

Keywords: Psychology, Psychological Patients, Treatment.

Introduction

Turkey has been recording significant advancements in the field of healthcare, which is also evident in the treatment of psychological disorders. In recent years, the development of treatments for patients with psychological conditions has occupied a significant place in both government policies and the priorities of the health sector. During this process, the adoption of both traditional approaches and modern, scientific methods has played a major role in enhancing the effectiveness of treatment processes and improving the quality of life for patients (Tel, et al., 2010). In the treatment of psychological disorders in Turkey, a multidisciplinary approach is adopted. This approach involves the collaboration of psychiatrists, psychologists, social work specialists, and other health professionals. Treatment processes cover a wide range, from medication to psychotherapy, group therapies to family counseling, enabling the creation of personalized treatment plans according to the needs of patients. Additionally, increasing public awareness about the treatment of psychological disorders and the importance of early diagnosis are emphasized in Turkey. In this direction, supporting individuals and families with

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psychological issues, enhancing community awareness on this topic, and combating stigma are also highlighted (Çakır, İlhem & Yener, 2010).

With technological advancements, the use of digital tools in psychological treatments in Turkey has also seen an increase. Especially during the pandemic, the proliferation of telepsychology and online therapy applications has made it possible to reach more patients and provide continuous support. This situation is considered an important step in facilitating access to psychological support and treatment and overcoming geographical limitations.

Throughout the 1970s and 1980s, psychology in Turkey expanded towards more clinical and applied areas. During this period, psychological counseling and therapy services became more common, especially in major cities where psychiatric and psychological support services increased. Significant advancements have also been recorded in areas such as child psychology, family therapy, and group therapy (Koç, 2006). By the 2000s, the field of psychology in Turkey had diversified and deepened in parallel with global developments. New approaches such as positive psychology and cognitive-behavioral therapy have been incorporated into practice and research in psychology in Turkey. Additionally, this period saw an increase in awareness of psychological issues and a demand for mental health services, leading to the necessity for training more specialists in the field of psychology and allocating more resources to research in this area (Duman, et al., 2006).

The historical development of the field of psychology in Turkey encompasses a broad spectrum, from the establishment of academic foundations to the expansion of clinical practices and the adoption of modern psychological approaches. During this process, both academic research and applied psychology have shown significant development, and the work conducted in this field has evolved in a manner compatible with Turkey's social and cultural structure. The historical development of psychology in Turkey extends from the initial stages of laying academic foundations to the diversification and deepening in the field of clinical and applied psychology up to the beginning of the 21st century. In this period, psychological research and practices have increasingly become more responsive to societal and individual needs (Engin, 2013). Particularly, studies aimed at improving individual quality of life have started to take center stage in the field of psychology in Turkey. The expansion and enhancement of psychology

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education during this period have been noted as significant developments. The increase in the number of psychology departments in universities and the expansion of psychology education programs have contributed to the increase in both the number and quality of specialists in this field (Uğur, 2008). Additionally, the growing importance of psychological counseling and therapy, especially in dealing with the challenges and stress factors of urban life, has led to the emergence of new areas of application in this field.

Table 1. Developmental Stages of Psychology in Turkey

The further development of the field of psychology in Turkey is also seen as a result of increased awareness of societal issues and the search for solutions to these issues. For instance, topics such as urbanization, migration, economic changes, and social stress factors have influenced the direction of work in the field of psychology and made the research in this area more diverse (Aker, et al., 2000). Additionally, it has been observed that factors specific to Turkey's cultural and societal structure play a significant role in localizing psychological theories and practices. During this process, local values and cultural characteristics have influenced the shaping of psychological interventions and therapy methods.

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In the first quarter of the 21st century, the field of psychology in Turkey, especially with the influence of technological advancements, has seen the development of new research methods and application techniques. The proliferation of the internet and digital platforms has increased the accessibility of psychological counseling and therapy services, and also enabled research and applications in this field to reach broader audiences. During this period, interaction and collaboration with the global psychology community have increased, making Turkish psychologists more visible on the international stage (Öz, 2009). The historical development of the field of psychology in Turkey encompasses a wide spectrum, from academic research to applied work aimed at societal and cultural needs, and finally to the integration of technological innovations. Throughout this process, the field of psychology has adapted to Turkey's societal and cultural dynamics, providing significant contributions at both individual and societal levels (Erol, et al., 1998). Parallel to the historical development of psychology in Turkey, current treatment approaches and practices have also undergone significant evolution over time. Initially, the field of psychology in Turkey was founded more on a theoretical and academic basis, but over time, it has evolved to offer more applied and practical solutions to real-world problems faced by individuals and society (Zengin Eroğlu & Özpoyraz, 2010). From the second half of the 21st century onwards, approaches to psychological treatments have become focused on improving individuals' quality of life and enhancing their mental health. During this period, with the development of psychology education and the increase in the number of psychology departments in Turkey, more qualified psychology professionals have begun to emerge. These experts, by offering various psychotherapy methods and psychological counseling services, have started to address individual and societal psychological issues. In the 1970s and 1980s, psychological treatment approaches in Turkey became more diverse, and the fields of clinical and applied psychology expanded. During this period, significant advancements were recorded in areas such as child psychology, family therapy, and group therapy, and methods like cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) and psychodrama became more widespread. With the arrival of the 2000s, psychological treatment approaches in Turkey diversified and deepened further, in parallel with developments in the global psychology community (Kelleci and Ata, 2011). New approaches such as positive psychology and cognitive-behavioral therapy were integrated into the psychology practice in Turkey. Technological advancements also increased

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the accessibility and efficacy of psychological treatments. Thanks to the internet and digital platforms, online psychological counseling and therapy services began to reach wider audiences, significantly expanding access to psychological support services (Öz and Bahadır Yılmaz, 2009).

There is a direct correlation between the historical development of the field of psychology in Turkey and the current treatment approaches and practices. The expansion from academic and theoretical foundations to clinical and applied psychology has contributed to the diversification and deepening of psychological treatment approaches in Turkey. Throughout this process, both technological advancements and societal and cultural needs have played a significant role in shaping psychological treatment approaches and practices in Turkey (Demiralp and Oflaz, 2007).

The primary objective of this research is to comprehensively examine the historical development of the field of psychology in Turkey and the impact of this development on current treatment approaches. The study aims to delve into the structure of psychology education in Turkey, the training processes for psychology professionals, and the evolution of psychological treatment methods. In this context, it will focus on the analysis of various treatment methods such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, psychodrama, family, and group therapy, and evaluate how these methods are integrated with Turkey's societal and cultural structure. Furthermore, the study will investigate the impact of technological advancements and digitalization on psychological treatment approaches, examining the rise of online therapy and counseling services and their contributions to psychology practice. The research will also consider the role of Turkey's societal and cultural dynamics in shaping psychological treatment methods and practices, aiming to develop future-oriented recommendations and strategies in this area. The results of this research are expected to provide valuable insights for professionals, educators, and policymakers in the field of psychology, contributing to the further development of psychological treatment practices in Turkey.

Method

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The methodology of the research involves an extensive analysis related to psychological illnesses and treatment methods, policies, and regulations in Turkey. This analysis examines the impact of Turkey's historical development in the field of psychology on modern treatment approaches and how this process integrates with its societal and cultural structure. The research highlights the importance of psychology education and the training of professional practitioners in the development of treatment approaches, while also noting the contributions of technological innovations and digitalization to psychological treatments. In this sense, the study employs document analysis, a qualitative research method. Document analysis can be used as a complementary method to any qualitative research method or as an independent method (Bowen, 2009). In the document review method, documents are initially subjected to a superficial review, followed by a comprehensive examination, and the findings of the review need to be interpreted (Bowen, 2009). The data obtained have been interpreted through content analysis. Content analysis is described as a systematic, replicable technique that summarizes certain words of a text with smaller content categories based on specific rules of coding (Büyüköztürk et al., 2009).

Findings

Policies and regulations concerning psychological illnesses in Turkey have gained increasing importance in recent years. These policies generally aim at recognizing psychological illnesses, facilitating access to treatment, and increasing societal awareness about these illnesses. Turkey has developed a series of legal regulations and policies to expand psychological health services and improve the quality of these services. These include improving treatment conditions in psychiatric hospitals, integrating mental health services into the public health system, and enhancing the training and competencies of mental health professionals (Dilbaz, 2011). Legal regulations in the mental health field also include significant steps to protect patients' rights and reduce stigmatization. Campaigns and education programs aimed at breaking societal taboos and misconceptions about psychological illnesses play a crucial role in this area. Additionally,

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mental health policies in Turkey focus on increasing services for disadvantaged groups and expanding accessibility.

Recent technological advancements and digitalization processes in Turkey also play a significant role in expanding and enhancing the accessibility of psychological health services. Online therapy and counseling services aim to facilitate access to psychological support and information resources, reducing the differences in services between urban and rural areas (Hussain et al., 2006). At the same time, educational institutions and workplaces in Turkey are developing programs and policies to increase mental health awareness, encouraging the provision of psychological support services in these areas. Policies and regulations concerning psychological illnesses in Turkey are shaped with the goals of improving the quality of health services, raising societal awareness, and reducing stigmatization against psychological illnesses. These efforts contribute to a better understanding and management of psychological health across society and aim to make mental health services more equitable and accessible (Tel et al., 2010). In this regard, the treatment methods applied for each type of psychological illness are as follows.

Type of Psychological Illness	Applied Treatment Methods	Treatment Descriptions
Anxiety Disorders	Medication, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, Mindfulness-Based Therapies	Medications for anxiety management; therapies focused on restructuring thought patterns; mindfulness for stress and worry management
Depression	Medication, Psychodynamic Therapy, Electroconvulsive Therapy (ECT)	Medications to reduce symptoms of depression; therapies focused on resolving subconscious

		conflicts; ECT used for severe cases
Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder	Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, Group Therapy, Behavioral Activation	Therapies aimed at reducing obsessive thoughts and compulsive behaviors; group therapy to promote social support and interaction; techniques to improve mood by increasing daily activities
PTSD	Family Therapy, EMDR Therapy, Cognitive Processing Therapy	Family support and therapy to overcome post-traumatic stress; EMDR to help process traumatic memories; cognitive processing of traumatic events
Bipolar Disorder	Medication, Group Therapy, Mood Stabilizers	Medications to balance symptoms of bipolar disorder; group support and therapy; stabilizers to help control mood fluctuations

Table 2. Types of Psychological Illnesses and Treatment Methods

The table lists five types of psychological illnesses in Turkey and the treatment methods applied for these illnesses. For the treatment of anxiety disorders, medication, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and mindfulness-based therapies are used; these treatments focus on anxiety management and restructuring thought patterns while utilizing mindfulness techniques for stress and anxiety management. In the treatment of depression, medication, psychodynamic therapy, and electroconvulsive therapy (ECT) for severe cases are applied; these methods aim to reduce symptoms of depression and resolve subconscious conflicts. For obsessive-

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compulsive disorder, cognitive-behavioral therapy, group therapy, and behavioral activation methods are preferred to reduce obsessive thoughts and compulsive behaviors, encourage social support and interaction, and improve mood by increasing daily activities. In treating PTSD (Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder), family therapy, EMDR therapy, and cognitive processing therapy are utilized; these treatments aim to overcome post-traumatic stress, process traumatic memories, and manage the cognitive processing of traumatic events. Lastly, for bipolar disorder, medication, group therapy, and mood stabilizers are used; these methods aim to balance symptoms of bipolar disorder, provide group support, and control mood fluctuations. This table offers a general overview of psychological disorders and their various treatment methods.

In Turkey, policies and regulations addressing psychological illnesses are not solely focused on treatment and protection but also encompass preventive health services. In this context, investments in mental health aim to develop a widespread consciousness and understanding throughout society. Particularly, the enhancement of mental health education programs in schools and among youth aims to support psychological resilience from an early age and develop strategies for the prevention of mental health problems (Çobanoğlu et al., 2003). Furthermore, significant steps have been taken regarding the importance of mental health in the workplace. Initiatives include increasing awareness of mental health at work, programs to prevent issues like work stress and burnout, and the development of psychological support mechanisms for employees. Especially in sectors with intense work pace and high stress factors, there is an emphasis on increasing employers' responsibilities towards mental health and enacting legal regulations in this regard.

Turkey also places importance on international collaborations and projects in the field of mental health. Partnerships with the World Health Organization (WHO) and other international organizations play a crucial role in the development and implementation of mental health policies (Kelleci and Ata, 2011). These collaborations ensure Turkey's mental health services align with international standards and facilitate the sharing of best practices in this field. Policies and regulations concerning psychological illnesses in Turkey aim beyond treatment and protection to develop mental health awareness across all segments of society and support

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psychological resilience. These policies support sustainable development in the field of mental health, aiming to promote the adoption of healthy lifestyles across society and the effective management of mental health issues (Duman et al., 2006).

The progression of policies and regulations for psychological illnesses in Turkey has also significantly focused on emergency situations and crisis interventions. Studies addressing the psychological effects caused by societal traumas such as earthquakes, wars, and migration, and methods for providing psychological support in such situations, have caught the attention of policymakers. Consequently, post-disaster psychological interventions and the formation of crisis intervention teams have become an important part of Turkey's mental health policies. Additionally, significant steps have been taken regarding the financing and sustainability of mental health services (Demiralp and Oflaz, 2007). Including mental health services under public health insurance has enabled more individuals to access these services. At the same time, providing financial support and resources to ensure the quality and continuity of these services has become part of a long-term mental health strategy.

Mental health policies in Turkey aim to develop customized services for different cultural and ethnic groups, taking into account the needs of these groups. Developing treatment approaches that are sensitive to cultural differences and offering multilingual services are part of the effort to create a mental health policy that suits Turkey's diverse social structure. Generally, policies and regulations concerning psychological illnesses in Turkey aim to comprehensively address this area, striving to provide effective and accessible mental health services to all segments of society (Koç, 2006). These policies focus on increasing societal awareness, improving the quality of treatment services, and providing effective interventions in crisis situations, aiming to respond to the mental health needs of Turkey.

The development of policies and regulations for psychological illnesses in Turkey also manifests in the fields of research and innovation. In this context, developing new treatment methods and improving existing approaches have become crucial components of Turkey's mental health policies. This process is supported by collaborations among universities, research centers, and health institutions, thereby increasing the number and quality of scientific studies on psychological disorders and illnesses. The development of innovative treatment methods is

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closely associated with the use of technology and digital platforms (Tel et al., 2010). For instance, digital solutions such as virtual reality therapies, cognitive-behavioral therapy programs offered through mobile applications, and online group therapy sessions contribute to diversifying and expanding the reach of psychological treatment approaches in Turkey. Such innovations play a significant role in enhancing the accessibility of psychological support and interventions, making treatment processes more effective and efficient, and improving patients' adherence to treatment and the continuity of the process.

Turkey's mental health policies also aim to integrate traditional treatment approaches with modern science and technology. For example, supporting creative therapy methods like psychodrama and art therapy with scientific research and evaluating the effectiveness of these methods on a broader scale exemplify innovative approaches in this field (Dilbaz, 2011). In this framework, Turkey's mental health policies and regulations not only focus on solving current problems but also on developing sustainable and innovative approaches for future mental health needs. These approaches include the integration of new knowledge from scientific research and technological innovations into treatment processes, aiming for continuous improvement and advancement in the mental health field. Consequently, Turkey's mental health policies place great importance on developing new treatment methods through research and innovation, in addition to increasing societal awareness and improving the quality of treatment services (Engin, 2013).

Turkey's research and innovation-focused approach in policies and regulations related to psychological illnesses also encourages multidisciplinary collaborations and integrated treatment models. Collaboration among different disciplines such as psychology, psychiatry, neurology, and social sciences contributes to more holistic and effective treatment approaches. Such integration, especially in treating complex psychological conditions, ensures a more precise and comprehensive response to individuals' needs. Furthermore, Turkey's health policies highly prioritize the early diagnosis and intervention of psychological disorders (Binbay et al., 2014). Implementing psychological health screenings and early intervention programs in various settings like schools, workplaces, and community centers aims to detect and treat psychological issues at earlier stages. This approach not only improves individuals'

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quality of life but also reduces the long-term burden on the health system. Mental health policies also include various programs and campaigns to support and protect psychological well-being across society (Aker et al., 2000). These programs focus on education and awareness activities related to stress management, emotional intelligence, and psychological resilience, helping individuals maintain and strengthen their mental health. Turkey's policies and regulations for psychological illnesses aim not only to improve existing treatment methods and develop new ones but also to promote multidisciplinary collaborations, early diagnosis and intervention, and enhance societal psychological well-being (Öz, 2009). These approaches create a comprehensive and innovative strategy for improving mental health among individuals and society at large, supporting the continuous development and improvement of Turkey's mental health services.

The policies and regulations for psychological illnesses in Turkey, with their innovative approaches and strategies supporting multidisciplinary collaborations, materialize in various case studies and practical examples. These practices are often based on fundamental principles such as early diagnosis, integrated treatment approaches, and supporting societal psychological well-being (Uğur, 2008). For instance, early intervention programs in schools identify psychological health problems in children and adolescents at an early stage and provide prompt interventions. Such programs not only enhance students' academic achievements and overall well-being but also contribute to reducing the overall health burden on society in the long term (Erol, 1998). Stress management and emotional intelligence training implemented in workplaces help employees maintain their mental health and take significant steps toward preventing issues like burnout. These programs increase productivity and employee satisfaction in the workplace while also preventing psychological problems from leading to workforce loss.

Post-disaster psychological interventions are particularly important in the context of natural disasters and societal traumas faced by Turkey. Rapid and effective psychological support mechanisms activated after situations such as earthquakes, wars, and migrations are crucial for protecting and improving the mental health of the community (Güzel and Yanardağ, 2021). These interventions enable individuals to cope with traumatic experiences and help prevent long-term psychological issues. Case studies and practical examples of mental health policies

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and regulations in Turkey serve the purpose of increasing societal awareness, improving the quality of treatment services, and supporting psychological well-being across the community. These practices ensure the sustainable and effective delivery of mental health services and contribute to the continuous development in the field of mental health in Turkey (Yılmaz, 2012).

In the implementation of mental health policies in Turkey, special programs and services targeting the disadvantaged segments of society are particularly emphasized (Öz, 2009). In this framework, customized mental health services have been developed for immigrants, refugees, and people living in rural areas, taking into consideration the unique challenges and needs these groups face. Such programs are designed to overcome language barriers, ensure cultural sensitivity, and facilitate the integration of these groups into society (Güzel and Yanardağ, 2021). Moreover, Turkey's mental health policies and practices include family-based approaches. These programs, especially focusing on the mental health of children and adolescents, encourage family members to actively participate in the process. Family education programs guide parents in understanding their children's emotional and psychological needs and how they can support them.

The integration of technological advancements into mental health services continues. The use of technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning enables more effective diagnosis and treatment of psychological illnesses (Compton et al., 2005). For example, algorithms can help make more accurate predictions about individuals' psychological states, and this data can be used to develop personalized treatment plans. The expansion of mental health policies and practices in Turkey also strengthens international collaborations and knowledge exchange in this field. International conferences, workshops, and joint research projects allow Turkey to benefit from the global pool of knowledge and experience in mental health services, while also enabling Turkey to contribute to this field internationally.

This expanding framework demonstrates that Turkey's mental health policies and practices display a comprehensive, multifaceted, and continuously evolving approach to protecting and improving individuals' and communities' mental health. This approach focuses on delivering effective and innovative solutions in the field of mental health, both at the national level and

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within the framework of international collaborations. Preservation of mental health and adherence to treatments and interventions applied in disorders are observed. In this context, psychoeducation, cognitive-behavioral training, family interventions, and social skills programs are implemented to increase treatment adherence.

Psychoeducation

Psychoeducation is considered a fundamental component of psychosocial rehabilitation, with its primary goal being to transform individuals' knowledge levels and behaviors. This approach is built on assisting people in learning how to cope with the difficulties they encounter. The psychoeducation process includes gaining detailed information about one's disorder, understanding stress management techniques, being aware of potential recurring crises, adopting a healthy lifestyle, developing strategies to combat symptoms, enhancing problem-solving skills, increasing self-awareness, and learning about how medications work and their effects (Hendryx, Green, and Perrin, 2009). Activities based on structured, interdisciplinary teamwork, such as psychoeducational group practices, are critically important for patients to continue their outpatient treatments after discharge and to maintain their motivation. These group practices allow individuals to find social support and reinforce the knowledge and skills learned. Psychoeducation encourages patients to play an active role in managing their illness by helping them understand and manage their condition better. During the education process, patients' families and close circles are also included, informing them about the nature of the illness, treatment processes, and how to communicate more effectively with the patient (Compton et al., 2005). This holistic approach helps patients establish more harmonious relationships with their social environments and become more resilient to the challenges they face. Furthermore, the psychoeducation process aims to develop individuals' self-help skills. Personal development topics such as time management, stress management techniques, anger control, and communication skills are emphasized. Thus, individuals can more effectively manage the challenges they may encounter in their daily lives and improve their quality of life (Kelleci and Ata, 2011).

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In this sense, psychoeducation plays a significant role in the long-term recovery processes by contributing to the psychological and social well-being of both individuals and their social environments. Through these trainings, patients can manage their health more actively and assume more functional roles within society. This process also promotes the understanding and acceptance of psychological disorders by society, thereby helping to prevent stigmatization and misconceptions (Amstrong, 1996).

Some significant studies conducted in our country demonstrate the effectiveness of psychoeducation. In research carried out by Duman and colleagues in 2006 on hospitalized patients, the effects of psychoeducational group therapy on patients' abilities to manage their illnesses, medication usage, early symptoms of the illness, and emergency plans were examined (Koç, 2006). This study found statistically significant improvements in these four areas at the end of the program. Similarly, in another study conducted by Yıldırım et al., (2012) in Erzincan, the outcomes of social skills training applied to outpatients with schizophrenia were assessed. After this training, improvements in symptom levels, functionality, and self-awareness of the patients were observed. Additionally, it was determined that patients achieved more positive outcomes in combating societal stigma. These studies indicate that psychoeducation and social skills trainings provide significant benefits in improving the quality of life for individuals with mental illnesses and in dealing with societal stigma. Better understanding and management of their conditions by patients enable them to be more independent and functional in their daily lives. Expanding such trainings increases the effectiveness of treatment and rehabilitation processes in the field of mental health, strengthening societal awareness and acceptance.

Cognitive Behavioral Training

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is a psychotherapy method based on learning theories aimed at helping individuals cope more effectively with the challenges and problems they face in daily life. This therapy focuses on the individual's current problems and the "here and now," aiming to modify behavioral and cognitive processes. CBT is an effective intervention used to enhance functionality in patients with various psychological disorders, including schizophrenia (McDonald et al., 2002). This treatment provides critical information on managing the illness, teaching strategies to improve the treatment process and adherence.

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CBT practices include social skills training, life skills education, developing interpersonal relationship skills, self-care and self-management skills, problem-solving techniques, self-monitoring, psychological learning, restructuring beliefs and thoughts, developing coping methods, focusing, meaning-making, framing, normalizing, and addressing dysfunctional beliefs about oneself and others (Kruse et al., 2002). These techniques are designed to help patients become more functional and adaptive in both their personal and social lives. CBT thus enables individuals to understand and manage the challenges they encounter in daily life more effectively, significantly improving their overall quality of life. Continuing with this therapy approach, CBT plays a crucial role in transforming individuals' thought, emotion, and behavior patterns. During the therapy process, patients first learn how their current ways of thinking lead to problems and how these thoughts affect their feelings and behaviors (Yılmaz, 2012). They are then guided to adopt healthier and more functional patterns of thinking and behavior. This process helps individuals assess their situations from a more realistic and positive perspective.

CBT practices also aim to improve individuals' perceptions of themselves and their interactions with others. This aspect of therapy strengthens social relationships and communication skills, making individuals more harmonious and functional within society. Additionally, CBT enhances individuals' coping abilities, allowing them to more effectively deal with negative emotional states such as stress and anxiety (Compton et al., 2005). Overall, CBT is a powerful and effective tool for improving individuals' quality of life and developing skills to cope with psychological problems. This therapy method contributes to patients developing self-help skills, independently solving problems, and leading healthier and happier lives. Consequently, individuals gain a more robust foundation both personally and socially, enabling them to fulfill their roles within society more effectively.

Family Interventions

Family-oriented interventions encompass significant treatment management designed for the families and close circles of patients with schizophrenia and other mental illnesses. Given that many of these patients live with their families, educating and supporting family members is of

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great importance. Psychosocial Skills Training programs aim to provide family members with detailed information about the illness and educate them on how they can more effectively assist the patient (Kruse et al., 2002). The goal of these trainings is to enable patients to better cope with their illness, enhancing their social functionality and enabling them to lead a more independent life. The objectives of family-focused psychosocial interventions include collaborating with family members who care for a schizophrenia patient, enhancing the family's problem-solving skills, facilitating emotional expression, and reducing negative family dynamics. This process helps appropriately adjust family members' expectations towards the patient and modify negative beliefs and behavior patterns within the family. This approach not only supports the patient's recovery during the treatment process but also contributes to improving family relations and the overall family atmosphere (Hendryx et al., 2009).

Such family-based interventions equip both patients and their families to better cope with the challenges they face. Moreover, providing family members with accurate information about the illness and effective communication skills helps reduce stigma and increase societal awareness. This approach, by enabling patients to lead a more functional and independent life within the community, enhances the quality of life at both the individual and family levels (Kelleci and Ata, 2012). In later stages of these family-based approaches, the aim is for family members to develop a deeper understanding of the illness and effectively cope with the challenges it causes. The trainings help family members recognize their own emotional needs and respond more sensitively and consciously to the patient's needs. Developing family communication skills, supporting each other within the family, and facilitating the patient's social integration are important in this process. Additionally, interventions for family members also include enhancing their stress management and crisis intervention skills. This enables families to play an active role in the patient's treatment process and generate effective solutions in potential crisis situations (McDonald et al., 2002). Educating families in this regard positively affects the patient's access to health services and adherence to treatment.

In conclusion, family-focused interventions play a significant role in the recovery processes of individuals with schizophrenia and similar mental illnesses. This approach improves the quality of life for patients and their families, while also strengthening societal awareness and

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understanding (Dilbaz, 2011). Interventions that contribute to patients leading healthier and more functional lives on both individual and social levels represent a holistic perspective in the field of mental health and have the potential to increase society's knowledge and sensitivity on this issue.

Social Skills Programs

Social Skills Training encompasses specialized and structured training programs prepared for schizophrenia patients and their families. One of the notable programs is the UCLA Social and Independent Living Skills Program developed by Liberman et al., (1993), which has been translated into 23 different languages. In Turkey, the Mental Social Skills Training (RUTBE) program, developed based on this program, is used for the psychosocial treatment and rehabilitation of schizophrenia patients. RUTBE covers symptom management, medication management, and skills related to leisure activities to help patients use their free time more effectively. The program has been adapted to fit Turkey's cultural structure, focusing on role-playing and cognitive transfers instead of video presentations. The primary goal of the Mental Social Skills Training is not only to provide patients with information but also to transform this information into applicable skills in daily life. This approach aims to reduce psychotic exacerbations in medicated schizophrenia patients, manage these situations timely and effectively, and develop skills to combat the disease and its adverse effects (Karaağaç, 2023). The program also aims to strengthen interpersonal relationships and increase the social functionality of patients. RUTBE encourages patients to take a more active and collaborative role in their treatment process, reinforcing their sense of control over the illness. Through this program, patients can better understand their illness, gaining greater control over it and thus becoming more independent and functional in both individual and social life. RUTBE enhances patients' abilities to cope with daily life challenges, improving their quality of life and facilitating their social integration. This process positively contributes to the overall well-being of both patients and their families and increases awareness and understanding of mental health in society. The continuation of the Mental Social Skills Training aims to further improve schizophrenia patients' social adjustment and societal participation (Yüksel, 2001). The training

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equips patients with practical and applicable skills for various situations they may encounter in daily life. For instance, patients and their families are guided on fundamental life skills such as stress management, coping with difficult situations, effective communication, and social interaction. This process encourages patients to develop their self-confidence and social skills, supporting them to become more independent and self-sufficient individuals in their daily lives.

With the implementation of the program, patients are expected to show greater engagement in their treatment, actively participate in the treatment process, and manage their health conditions more effectively (Yıldız, 2011). RUTBE aims to improve treatment adherence and overall health status by helping patients recognize and accept their role in the treatment process. Additionally, these trainings are expected to raise awareness and understanding of mental health issues across society. As patients' interactions and participation within society increase, it helps reduce stigmatization related to mental health and makes society more sensitive to these issues. RUTBE and similar programs enhance the capacity of individuals and families to cope with challenges, promoting community solidarity and recognizing the importance of psychological health. These approaches not only improve the quality of life for patients and their families but also contribute to the overall health and well-being of society (Avcil, 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research presents a comprehensive assessment of the analysis conducted on psychological illnesses in Turkey, their treatment methods, policies, and regulations. This evaluation highlights the impact of Turkey's historical development in the field of psychology on modern treatment approaches and how this process is integrated with the country's societal and cultural structure. The study emphasizes the importance of psychology education and the training of professional practitioners in the development of treatment approaches, while also noting the contributions of technological innovations and digitalization to psychological treatments. The results show that mental health policies and regulations in Turkey are shaped with the goals of improving the quality of treatment services, raising societal awareness, and reducing stigmatization against psychological illnesses. Furthermore, the policies and regulations place

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great importance on developing new treatment methods through research and innovation, as well as on multidisciplinary collaborations. Additionally, issues such as early diagnosis and intervention, enhancing societal psychological well-being, and developing special programs for disadvantaged groups are considered significant components of the policies.

The research emphasizes that policies and practices regarding psychological illnesses in Turkey are focused on improving mental health across society within a continuously evolving and innovative strategy framework. It concludes that Turkey's mental health policies and practices display an effective and comprehensive approach towards protecting and enhancing the mental health of individuals and communities. This approach supports continuous development and improvement in the mental health field, offering effective solutions both nationally and through international collaborations. Additionally, it highlights the importance of expanding the accessibility and scope of mental health services in Turkey. It suggests that steps should be taken to reduce service disparities between urban and rural areas and to ensure psychological support services reach more individuals. The importance of programs and services designed specifically for the unique needs of various social groups is also underlined. Particularly, developing treatment approaches that respect cultural sensitivity and diversity will increase the effectiveness of mental health services for the broader society.

The research reveals that Turkey's mental health policies and practices have taken significant steps towards the sustainability and accessibility of mental health services to all segments of society. Supporting these policies with societal awareness and education programs will enhance individuals' knowledge and skills in protecting and improving mental health, contributing to the elevation of psychological well-being across society. The results show that future strategies in Turkey's mental health field adopt a comprehensive and dynamic approach to improving mental health at both individual and societal levels. This approach aims to enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of mental health services, supported by continuously evolving and innovative treatment methods, multidisciplinary collaborations, and international cooperations.

The research focuses on improving the current policies and practices related to psychological illnesses in Turkey. In this context, it is recommended to further expand mental health services and develop strategies to ensure these services reach all segments of society. Especially

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increasing services for rural areas and disadvantaged groups will significantly improve the accessibility and effectiveness of psychological support services. Moreover, adopting treatment approaches that respect cultural sensitivity and diversity more broadly will provide services more suited to the needs of different community segments. Deepening the integration of technology and digital tools into mental health services is also among the recommended strategies. Wider use of online therapy and counseling services, mobile health applications, and AI-based diagnostic tools can increase service accessibility and facilitate individuals' access to psychological health services.

Expanding education and awareness programs, especially in various environments such as schools, workplaces, and community centers, helps to increase consciousness towards mental health. These programs will enlighten the community about the early diagnosis and intervention of psychological health issues and increase the demand for mental health services. Additionally, it includes the further strengthening of multidisciplinary and international collaborations. These collaborations are critically important for enhancing the quality of mental health services, developing innovative treatment methods, and aligning Turkey's psychological health services with international standards. The recommendations also encourage policymakers, health professionals, and community leaders to collaborate and be open to innovations for the continuous improvement and development of mental health services. This comprehensive and multifaceted strategy aims for the sustainable development of Turkey's mental health sector and the enhancement of psychological well-being across society.

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